

Designing Pleasure; Designers' Needs

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Abstract

A series of interviews with academic and practicing designers was carried out to inform the development of a 'pleasure resource' that designers can use to enable understanding of the emotional needs of specific markets, at an early stage of the design process. In order to produce such a resource, it was necessary to investigate the attitudes and needs of designers on the subject of 'pleasure' in design.

Findings show that designers are aware of the necessity to satisfy the emotional needs of the user, but there has to be a compromise with other factors e.g. production costs. Those interviewed tended to rely upon 'quick and dirty' research methods, with few aware of techniques and data that relate specifically to user pleasure. They expressed great interest in a 'pleasure resource' that gave them access to information about specific market groups' emotional needs. Several designers suggested a greater focus on user 'lifestyle' information to promote empathy with users. The information collected has led to the development of several concept resources for detailed evaluation by designers.

Keywords: designers, pleasure

Introduction

'It is a rare designer or design team, that is inspired by anonymous descriptions of capacities, limitations and bell-curved representations of users.' (Fulton Suri, 2000)

Outlined in this paper are a series of interviews conducted with academic and practising designers. They form part of a wider ongoing programme of research into the development of a 'pleasure' resource for designers. The resource is intended to inform and guide designers from the start of the design process, providing data on the 'pleasure' needs of their target market. Research to date has focused on designer needs for a 'pleasure resource', in order to make the final outcome more useful and usable.

Context for research

An appreciation of the 'pleasure' values of products is of growing importance to the design industry and the consumer. People have come to expect high quality products, with good functionality and usability, and it has been suggested that these factors no longer drive consumer choice. Consumers now look for more from the products that they buy; they are looking for pleasure and the fulfilment of their emotional needs.

At present, designers provide the pleasure/emotional input through intuitive techniques, lacking any formal methodology. Additionally, the traditional usability approaches of ergonomists tend to view user satisfaction as the 'avoidance' of negative sensations rather than the promotion of positive ones (Jordan, 1999). Jordan (2000) argues that in today's consumer market 'good' human factors and 'good' design are expected and usability is no longer a satisfier, but a dissatisfier i.e. usability is a pre-requisite, where it is poor the user is dissatisfied. This approach goes beyond usability, incorporating pleasure into the designed artefact.

A 'pleasure' resource for designers

Methods do exist that enable the formalisation of the design of pleasurable aspects of products, e.g. Kansei engineering (Nagamachi, 1995). However, these methods have a product centred approach, and are utilised mainly for product evaluation late in the design process, often after many crucial decisions have been made. In this programme of research we are proposing a more human-centred approach. By creating a resource suitable for use at the beginning of the design process, to guide and focus the design direction. In a previous study (Porter, Chhibber, and Porter, 2002) data concerning peoples' attitudes towards the products they buy were collected and classified in a 'four-pleasure' framework (Jordan, 1997); physio-pleasure, socio-pleasure, psycho-pleasure and ideo-pleasure. A rudimentary database of peoples' most pleasurable products was also developed. Informal evaluation by designers indicated that a 'pleasure' resource would be of great value to designers.

The current programme of research involves the collection of general trend data concerning attitudes to product pleasure and product preference that can be statistically evaluated to highlight trends across a large sample size. Running concurrently with this, is a smaller sample of much richer, more intimate data from people discussing their most pleasurable

products (collected through video interviews). A critical issue in the research project is how this data will be delivered to designers.

Communication gap

Ergonomics input into the design process is immensely valuable (Feeney and Bobjer, 2000). However, there has traditionally been a communication ‘gap’ between the two disciplines. Porter and Porter (1999) cite that the differences between the two (and other related disciplines) may be due to consequences of innate ability, education, and the real world practices of the different disciplines. Most human factors methods are quantitative or qualitative, and are essentially analytical tools. They provide data about people’s capabilities and reactions to design variables, but do not generally lead directly to design solutions; often leaving the designer frustrated (Fulton Suri and Marsh, 2000). The data are often in a scientific non-prescriptive form which the designer finds hard to interpret (Feeney and Bobjer, 2000). This leads to human factors information frequently being left out of the design process (Bruder, 2000; Burns and Vincente, 2000), or being used in an inappropriate way (Burns and Vincente, 1994).

Porter and Porter (1999) highlight three factors behind the communication rift.

1. Communication of ergonomics information at an inappropriate point in the design process.
2. Communication difficulties between ergonomists and designers/engineering designers caused mainly by educational and practice differences.
3. Communication of ergonomics information and data in an inappropriate fashion by ergonomists.

Feeney and Bobjer (2000) note that a multi-disciplinary approach can be perceived by designers as intruding into their skill area, and that there is a general pre-occupation with technology and aesthetics within the design community. Ergonomics is also seen as costly, and of low value and accessibility by designers (Burns and Vincente, 1994). Hasdogan (1996) concludes that much ergonomic data is geared towards workplace circumstances and the trained user, and that information is presented in forms more suited to ergonomists than designers.

Designers' needs

Clearly the format of ergonomic information and its point of input into the design process are critical. Methods exist that enable the classification and evaluation of user 'pleasure', e.g. SEQUAM (Bandini-Buti L, Bonapace L, and Tarzia A, 1997), but little is known about what methods designers are aware of or are currently using. There is also a need to understand what types of information designers would like in a 'pleasure' resource and crucially, how they would like to access it. A series of interviews were conducted with academic and practicing designers in order to investigate these issues.

Designer interviews

Aims

1. Investigate the current level of understanding in the design community of 'user pleasure' and related research methods.
2. Investigate designer requirements for a resource intended to enable a greater understanding of the pleasure needs of their target market.
3. Begin to develop concepts of how a 'pleasure' resource may function.

Method

A series of informal interviews were conducted with 14 student and academic designers, six of whom had some degree of industrial experience. The survey results and a rudimentary 'pleasure' resource from a previous investigation (see Figure 1; Porter, Chhibber, and Porter, 2002, 2003) formed the basis of the interviews, and facilitated further discussion. Informal notes were taken and participants were provided with drawing equipment to help illustrate any ideas for a 'pleasure' resource. The discussion initially covered attitudes towards 'user pleasure' and related research methods, before focusing in on the development of a 'pleasure' resource, and what needs designers may have. A summary of the topics discussed and the responses are given below.

To what extent do you consider user 'pleasure' when designing?

The participants did consider user pleasure when they were designing, but the emphasis tended to be placed on aesthetic appeal and eliciting pleasure through the senses. Less attention was given to providing pleasure through other means, e.g. designing to suit specific social contexts. Those with some industrial experience noted that other issues e.g. cost, often became overriding factors.

What methods (if any) do you use to gain a more holistic view of the user, with a particular focus on designing in 'pleasure'?

The majority of interviewees utilised methods such as focus groups and questionnaires and took an iterative approach to designing. It was clear that research information was assessed in an intuitive way, with few designers having a strategy for gaining a more holistic view of the user. There was a focus on research methods that led directly to design decisions, e.g. user trials, rather than ones that focused on people and their emotions. It was evident that 'quick and dirty' methods were often used to gain information, with trials typically involving small sample sizes. No interviewees were aware of research methods that specifically addressed user 'pleasure'.

To what extent would a 'pleasure' resource about people and their emotional needs in relation to products assist in the design process?

The interviewees were shown the survey results and the paper database of pleasurable products from a previous study (Porter, Chhibber, and Porter, 2002). All of the interviewees felt that a 'pleasure' resource had a lot of potential to inform the design process. Nine interviewees noted that the 'four pleasure' framework (Jordan, 1997) was a useful structure to classify data in. Most added that it was useful to have the mixture of general information provided by the survey results, in conjunction with the 'richer' information provided by the data about peoples' most pleasurable products.

A couple of the interviewees raised the issue of updating the pleasure resource. It is undoubtedly true that certain trends and data will be somewhat 'outdated' after a few years, but the aim of the resource is to promote a wider understanding of the underlying issues behind why people gain pleasure from owning certain products, and it is these factors that

have a greater longevity. It is important to decide what is feasible in the remit and timescale of this research project.

What other information would you like a 'pleasure resource' to contain?

Several felt that a database of 'displeasurable' products would be beneficial. There was also a consensus that more user 'lifestyle' information was needed; promoting greater empathy. Suggestions ranged from details such as leisure interests, and personality profiles, to more abstract information such as a person's favourite films or food. However, there is a danger that many designers may base their decisions on just a few users who fit their 'ideal'. Consequently, it is important that the design of the resource must promote decision making based on an inclusive view of the user population.

The majority of interviewees wanted statistically valid information that provided a broad overview of the attitudes of the target market. Three liked the idea of having this information at the 'front end' of the resource, essentially forcing the designer to initially form a more inclusive view of the population they were designing for. However, care will have to be taken as going through this process each time would reduce the flexibility and freedom of the resource.

In what format would you like the information to be 'packaged'?

It was explained that the intention was to develop a computer based resource that allowed designers to browse information either via a software package or as a website. The designers were asked to 'brainstorm' around this brief and envisage how they would like to interact with such a resource. All of the designers wanted a flexible format, allowing access to the information in a number of different ways. The majority stated that they would like to specify the characteristics of their user (age/gender/income etc.) and then browse the results looking for trends and inspiration. While this flexibility and freedom must be provided, there must also be some mechanism in place that promotes an inclusive view of a user population.

Ten of the participants stated that they would also like to search just for the particular type of product that they are designing. This feature was seen as a quick inspirational tool during concept generation, or a feedback feature to check concepts against an existing bank of

‘pleasurable products’. Seven added that a virtual workspace or portfolio that can be used to store the information that they are gathering would be useful. These could then be printed off and used as a visual stimulus for concept generation and communication. All of the designers concluded that it was essential to have a visual and audio driven resource which was engaging and a ‘pleasure’ to use.

To what extent do you use/value visual information in the form of mood/influence boards in the design process?

Several subjects mentioned the use of mood boards during design research as a way of visually ‘encapsulating’ the user lifestyle. Some added that the creative process of making such visual resources was a key facet to their personal value, so the possibility of creating their own in a virtual workspace would be important.

Practicing designer interviews

The preliminary interviews were deliberately informal and open-ended. The procedure was refined and a more structured protocol was developed during the course of the interviews. A further series of interviews were then conducted with practicing designers to explore the issues raised in the preliminary interviews. In total, 14 practicing designers were interviewed. Of the 14, 11 were from industrial design consultancies, or in house design teams, and 3 were from slightly wider fields (interior design, exhibition/event design, and design project management).

A pre-interview information pack was developed (see Figure 2) and sent to the participants before their interview. The pack provided a comprehensive overview of the project and the interview they had agreed to take part in. It consisted of several different components; a cover letter, a brief overview document, interview cards (6 postcards, with an image and text relating to the six main topic areas of the interview with space for annotations), and an A3 storyboard illustrating a sample concept of the resource. In conjunction with the structured interview protocol, the information pack facilitated effective and useful interview sessions despite the much shorter timescale involved. Their views on the issues raised by the previous interviews are summarised below:

How important is user pleasure in the design process?

There was a consensus that 'user pleasure' is of real importance from the designers' perspective. However, when placed in the context of an actual design project, it becomes one of a number of factors that designers have to consider and make compromises between. Four of the designers added that they often argue the case for certain features if they feel that their inclusion would benefit the user and consequently, the client.

Across the sample, the practicing designers showed a greater awareness of pleasure in relation to the contextual and social issues of products, than the student and academic designers did. They were also more aware of the power and relevance of branding in relation to pleasure, and the way in which the products they were designing can both strengthen and communicate the brand.

What methods do you use to gain a more holistic understanding of the target user?

The majority of designers interviewed were strong advocates of user centred research in the design process. However, the volume of research, and the emphasis placed on it in the design process varied. Nine participants were from companies that appeared to place a greater emphasis on 'design through research'. Alternatively, five maintained a certain level of research, but tending towards a more intuitive design process. The majority took an iterative approach to the design process, revisiting the research data or conducting further research to guide design decisions.

Like the academic designers, the majority of practicing designers used traditional design research methods e.g. focus groups, to gain a more holistic view of the user. Unlike the academic designers, eight of the practicing designers also employed methods such as ethnography, role playing, and brainstorming, and 'live the life' research methods (visiting consumers in their homes and spending extended periods of time with them to witness their day to day activities first hand) to give a more intimate picture of their target consumer.

Traditionally, this kind of research may have been outsourced to a research company, but it was evident that designers have become increasingly active in the collection and analysis of data. However, across both the academic and practicing design groups, there did not appear

to be any real scientific rigour in the research. This is understandable given the nature of design education, and the time and cost restrictions inherent in most projects. The majority of interviewees were not aware of any pleasure specific research tools methods.

Would you find a pleasure resource useful?

There was a very positive response to the potential of the pleasure resource. Like the academic designers, many raised the issue of updating the resource and the dangers of trends becoming dated. A couple of the designers also questioned the scale of the resource and highlighted the fact that trends and information are likely to show variations across a country, but also across global regions.

There was concern from a couple of the interviewees about the role that the resource was intended to have in the design process and whether designers would misuse the resource by focusing too much on certain users in the database, or basing design decisions solely on information provided by the resource. This issue relates largely to the design education of the person using the resource; their willingness to design in an inclusive way and utilise their findings from the resource to guide and inform further first hand research.

What additional information would you like when designing?

The interviewees were satisfied with the type, quantity and relevance of the data that would be collected. In particular they liked the mix of information, ranging from statistically tested general data, to the more intimate rich data about specific individuals.

The majority of interviewees felt that information about brands would be very useful; perhaps peoples' most pleasurable brands as one participant suggested. Clearly, the interview participants work in a commercial setting, and as such the brand (either their own when working in-house or their clients for consultancy interviewees) plays a major role in the design of the product. Two of the designers also felt that information that allowed them to discover more about user groups' aspirations and attitudes would be useful.

There is a clear need for data about people that gives designers insight into their attitudes, aspirations, and lifestyle. It is also necessary to avoid producing bland 'marketing'

information that is of no use to the designer; clearly it has to be both inspirational and immersive.

How would you like the resource to function?

The designers wanted a flexible and intuitive resource that allowed access to information in several different ways. There was a consensus that information would have to be accessible at speed. A consequence of this demand is that the resource layout and structure must be logical and easy to learn. Additionally, the resource should be a visually stimulating and an interactive database. Concepts such as movie clips and sound clips, interactive user mood boards, and cut and paste workspaces where a designer could store information, were discussed with the interviewees. The majority would welcome this level of interactivity, as long as the speed of the process was not affected.

How important is visual information during the design process?

The interviewees unanimously agreed that visual information such as mood boards were the quickest and most effective way to communicate ideas and themes to a selection of people. They are for communication with clients and senior management, internally between designers, and to stimulate users during focus groups and workshops. Visual information in the form of video clips of individuals discussing their most pleasurable products was another proposed feature of the resource. The majority of interviewees felt that this would be valuable.

Conclusions

The interviews that formed this study have led to several conclusions that will aid in the development of a useful and usable 'pleasure' resource for designers. These are summarised below.

1. Satisfying user pleasure is of growing importance to designers, but is just one factor in the design of a product.

It is clear from the investigation that user 'pleasure' is of great importance to designers but, especially from a practicing designer's perspective, it is one of many factors that have to be considered and compromises made between during a design project. There has tended to be a focus on providing pleasure through aesthetic appeal and physio-pleasure, especially in the student and academic design community. It would appear that the realities of developing real products for clients and specific markets develops a designer's awareness of the social and contextual issues of 'pleasure' in relation to products and branding.

2. Designers are increasingly employing user centred design research methods to develop a more holistic view of the user, but methods are often 'quick and dirty' with an intuitive evaluation of data.

The majority of designers employ user centred design methods e.g. focus groups, however several practicing designers used less well known research techniques, e.g. video ethnography, to gain a more holistic view of their target market. There does not appear to be any scientific rigour or clear strategy to how research is carried out, and there is a reliance upon quick and dirty methods, with an intuitive application of results/data. There is clear evidence to support the development of a 'pleasure' resource, with few designers aware of any pleasure specific research tools/methods.

3. Designers require quick and easy access to information in the 'pleasure' resource. This information must immerse the designer in peoples' lifestyles in a highly visual and engaging way.

The investigation has led to several conclusions concerning the properties that a 'pleasure' resource must pose in order to satisfy the needs of designers. The resource must allow quick and easy access to information, and this must be done in an engaging way that appeals to designers. A key facet to this is the use of visual information (images, movie clips), and allowing access to this information in a flexible and intuitive way. The information in the resource is a mixture of statistically tested trend data, and richer intimate data about different individuals. The majority of the data will be structured around Jordan's (1997) four-pleasure framework. This format, and the data that will form the resource content was liked by designers, but there was clear indication that more lifestyle and branding information was

desired. The designers wanted a resource that allowed them to immerse themselves in peoples' lives, giving them greater empathy with a user group.

While it is crucial to satisfy designers needs, it is also important to develop mechanisms in the resource that promote inclusive design decisions, and reinforce the principle that the resource is a reference database aimed at inspiring and guiding design direction and research. It is not a replacement for user centred design and research, but a tool that guides the designer into the key issues of their target consumer earlier in the design process.

4. Development of resource concepts.

The interviews led to the development of several concept resources based on many of the principles and ideas discussed during the sessions. The academic interviews were loose and informal and several subjects sketched out concepts. These were developed and information from interviews with practicing designers led to further ideas and refinement. An example of a concept resource is shown below in Figures 3, 4, and 5. Figure 3 illustrates an opening search page where the designer has input criterion relating to a target market. In Figure 4 the designer is browsing one of several users who fit this market segment, looking at information such as their favourite products and brands. In Figure 5 the designer has accessed a high quality movie of the user talking about one of their most pleasurable products.

Future research

The series of interviews described in this paper have led to the development of several concept resources like the one illustrated in Figures 3-5. Future research focuses on an iterative development of a few concepts, with regular evaluation by designers. From this, the final resource will be developed and tested. Running concurrently with this is the development and implementation of a data collection strategy to acquire the information that forms the contents of the 'pleasure' resource.

Sample concept of pleasureable product resource

Figure 1, Sample concept of pleasure resource

Figure 2, Pre-interview information pack.

Figure 3, An opening search page where the designer has input criterion relating to a target market.

Figure 4, The designer is browsing one of several users who fit this market segment, looking at information such as their favourite products and brands

Figure 5, The designer has accessed a high quality movie of the user talking about one of their most pleasurable products

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Lynda Healey qualified in visual communication with a BA Hons in Manchester, in 1977. After a short time working for an advertising agency she returned to college to train as a teacher of Primary school children. Here she used art and craft work to communicate basic literacy and numeracy ideas. She taught for twenty years in inner city schools in Manchester and Birmingham. In 2002 she went to Birmingham Institute of Art and Design to do an MA in visual communication, where she produced an interactive multi-media project on basic literacy; graduating in 2003. She now works as a Research Associate in the Department of Design and Technology at Loughborough University developing the pleasure resource.